

**Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite
Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology
based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials**

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**D6.2 “Report on Communication, Dissemination and
Training Activities”
Work Package 6
Responsible Partner: Q-PLAN**

D6.2: Report on Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report” of the VIBES project, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. The main objective of VIBES is to develop and demonstrate a new, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

The document describes the overall communication and dissemination strategy, the means and channels for communication and dissemination, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and the partners’ responsibilities in this respect. It includes specific communication, dissemination and training activities that will be carried out by the VIBES consortium members in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results. The report outlines:

- **Why and what to disseminate:** the rationale of the project communication and dissemination strategy as well as the basic project-related information that will be conveyed throughout the project are presented in Chapter 2.
- **To whom:** the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project’s communication and dissemination campaign are also presented in Chapter 2.
- **By what means:** all the means and channels that will be used by project partners in order to successfully implement the communication, dissemination and training activities, are included in Chapters 3, 4 and 5 respectively.
- **When:** a time frame to ensure that the timing of the communication, dissemination and training activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project, is provided in Chapter 6.
- **Monitoring of the process:** the indicators to measure success on the communication, dissemination and training actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project, are identified in Chapter 7.

A second version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report” is foreseen to be submitted in the 18th month of the project, whereas a third version will be submitted in the 36th month and a final version in the 48th month of the project.

1. Introduction

VIBES aims to be a success story of collaboration among science, innovation and industrial entities from different countries to improve European Citizens wellbeing. Therefore, to communicate this story is of paramount importance to maximize project results and multiply the impact in European society.

The main aim of VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Plan is to provide the communication, dissemination and training strategy of the project. It will be updated and implemented during and after the project. Effective communication, dissemination and training activities will be carried out, following a good communication and dissemination strategy that will guarantee:

- Address audiences beyond the action's own community (including the media and the public).
- Objectives clearly defined.
- Creative and expert people involved on them to achieve highest impact.

Overall, the current communication, dissemination and training strategy report assists partners in designing and implementing their publicity, communication and engagement activities, within the framework of the project. It includes guidelines that can help achieve maximum visibility, so as to pave the way for a successful market uptake of the VIBES results. However, this report and its guidelines are subject to modifications and updates in line with the project progress and the experience that will be gained through the various project activities. As such, the communication, awareness raising and dissemination strategy that is presented in this report is not static. It is a living document that will be continuously reviewed in specific time intervals to account for any challenge or opportunity that may arise. A second version of the Communication, Dissemination and Training activities report is foreseen to be submitted in the 18th month of the project, whereas a third version will be submitted in the 36th month and a final version in the 48th month of the project.

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The objective of the Communication, Dissemination and Training plan is to target different audiences to create a European Identity, strengthening European Industry and building European Bridges. The main goals are:

1. To raise European citizens' awareness about cooperative research & innovation projects as the way to meet social challenges.
2. To facilitate the quick acceptance of breaking-edge technologies and innovative services within European industry.
3. To promote new, integrated business models, combining multi-criteria and multi-sectoral approach among decision-makers.

Therefore, clear messages will be part of the VIBES story to face the concerns of European audiences reaching at least 100,000 citizens, 1,500 EU industries (at different levels, including technicians) in interconnected sectors and 500 decision makers (public such as legal entities and private such as company directors and business developers).

VIBES stems from cooperation within a European consortium between organisations based in different EU countries that will allow to achieve better results, which would have otherwise been impossible. The project will validate a better use of resources to demonstrate the high potential of the Circular Economy with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation will be based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology, based on the development of smart Bio-based materials, applied for the first time to thermoset composites), which will equip the Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor. In addition, the VIBES approach will wide open the door to the manufacturing industry to design and produce enhanced components to boost jobs, growth and investment at European level. Finally, the inter-sectoral relationships as well as the project's shared objectives will influence the different decision makers, contributing to competitiveness and helping to meet social challenges.

The VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training plan guides the strategies that will set the key messages that should be sent from the partnership as well as the target audience, including gender balance aspects. The strategies will focus on target sectors related to the VIBES approach: composite materials, polymers, chemicals, logistics and transport, aeronautical, naval, energy and construction sectors among the main ones. To maximise the interest of the VIBES stakeholders, impact multipliers at the local, regional, national, European and global levels will be used (for instance, by taking advantage of networking with other identified BBI and H2020 projects, BIC and BBI channels). In addition, for the project's communication and dissemination activities, the consortium will identify media (press, magazines, radio programmes, thematic blogs, etc.) and events such as meetings, conferences, trade-fairs, workshops, training days, info-days, which are thematically close to the project. Moreover, a training plan will be aligned with the dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders for the envisaged new business and to science student profiles, in order to create a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.

1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables

This report will serve to present the impact on communication and dissemination that the project is having in different areas. This deliverable includes the communication and dissemination activities foreseen in Task 6.2 "Communication Implementation" and Task 6.3 "Dissemination Implementation" as well as the workshops, courses and training events foreseen in Task 6.4 "Training Implementation". The Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities is a horizontal action and the input for all relevant activities will come from the results and deliverables of all the other project work packages that include research, validation, pilot implementation and innovation actions.

As already mentioned above, updates of this report include deliverable D6.3 in month 18, deliverable D6.4 in month 36 and deliverable D6.5 in month 48 at the end of the project, compiling all the activities carried out in the field of communication, dissemination and training.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

With the above in mind, this initial version of the Communication, Dissemination and Training activities report, includes the VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Strategy and Plan, structured in 8 distinct chapters, as follows:

Chapter 1 - Introduction: it provides information about the scope of the report, its structure and its relationship with other activities and deliverables.

Chapter 2 - Communication and Dissemination Strategy: it defines a clear strategy for dissemination and communication activities by outlining the objectives, the target audiences, with reference to the Stakeholders Board and synergies with other projects and initiatives, the key messages, the key assets of VIBES, the partners' role and responsibilities and the gender dimension.

Chapter 3 - Communication Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels for carrying out the communication activities of the project, including the VIBES visual identity and promotional material, VIBES website and social media accounts, e-newsletters and press kit, participation in fairs and info-days and the Layman's report at the end of the project.

Chapter 3 - Dissemination Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels for carrying out the dissemination activities of the project, including publications to scientific journals, participation in scientific conferences and events, organisation of events, such as forums, roundtables, workshops and final conference.

Chapter 5 - Training Programme: it describes the training strategy and activities that are going to take place during the project to spread the idea of VIBES to younger generations of scientists and to industrial professionals.

Chapter 6 – Time Frame of Communication, Dissemination and Training activities: it provides a tentative time frame of the communication, dissemination and training activities, which will be updated during the course of the project.

Chapter 7 - Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting: it presents the way of monitoring and reporting the communication, dissemination and training activities, according to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set for those activities.

Chapter 8 - Conclusions: it summarises the conclusions of the Communication, Dissemination and Training Strategy and Plan, as well as the way forward.

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overview and Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of VIBES outlines the strategy that is going to be followed for every communication, dissemination and training activity foreseen for the entire project duration. For that reason, it is a document that will be largely connected with all the activities of the project's workplan.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy mostly aims to enable a wide reach and to contribute to a positive impact of the project, both exploiting the knowledge within the consortium and transferring the gained knowledge further to interested stakeholders. This strategy defines clear guidelines for all the dissemination and communication activities, which will be carried out throughout the project.

The VIBES communication and dissemination strategy can be summed up into the following main objectives:

- Promote the project's concept, activities, and events to interested target groups and stakeholders.
- Enhance the awareness of the project's goals and assets.
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities.
- Encourage participation in relevant conferences and other events.
- Disseminate the project's results and gained knowledge to the public.
- Establish liaisons and synergies with other relevant initiatives.
- Facilitate market uptake of the project's results.
- Define partners' responsibilities in communication and dissemination activities.
- Organise training courses and workshops so that the ideas and outcomes of VIBES will be further developed by younger generations of scientists and industrial professionals.

To ensure a successful outcome of the objectives mentioned above, the VIBES communication and dissemination strategy focuses on a practical and realistic plan including the appropriate means, channels and actions to spread the ideas of VIBES and engage the target audiences, but it also remains flexible and open to changes when necessary. The key element for a successful Communication and Dissemination Plan is a well-structured methodology based on **what we want to disseminate** (project assets), **to whom** (which target groups), **by what means** (press releases, social media, communication and dissemination tools, channels etc.), and **when to disseminate**. Keeping these in mind, the following steps emerge:

- Identify the project's aims and appropriate communication and dissemination channels to ensure maximum visibility.
- Identify the main target groups and appropriate communication and dissemination channels for each group.
- Identify the key messages and project's assets.
- Link communication and dissemination channels to each target group and define communication and dissemination tools and methods which will be used during the project.
- Establish the roles and responsibilities of the partners in executing and managing the project's communication and dissemination activities.
- Determine the stages of the communication and dissemination activities and overall timeline.

- Monitor key communication and dissemination indicators and adjust when necessary.

2.2 Target Audiences, Key Messages and Key Assets

2.2.1 The VIBES Target Audiences

All communication and dissemination activities will contribute to the overall aim of facilitating the widespread adoption of VIBES results, thus maximising the project’s impact. Therefore, it is essential to clearly specify the VIBES target audiences.

At this stage, the stakeholder groups that are illustrated in the following table have been identified as relevant to the VIBES project and, thus, represent the target audiences of the current communication and dissemination strategy.

Table 1. VIBES stakeholder groups and sub-groups

Group	Sub-group
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers
	Composite recyclers
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Aeronautical
	Naval
	Construction
	Energy
	Waste management
	Logistics
	Transport
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Academics and/or Researchers
	Technology and/or Innovation consultants
Impact multipliers	Policy makers
	Media/ journalists or bloggers

The identified stakeholder groups of the VIBES project are described below in more detail:

- **Industrial Developers:** industries that develop composite materials and/ or technologies for their recycling (thermoset composite material developers, composite recyclers).

- **Industrial Users:**
 - **Industrial Converters:** industries that manufacture equipment or build infrastructure, which includes parts made of composite materials, such as the aeronautical industry, the naval or shipbuilding industry, the construction and energy industries.
 - **Industrial Dismantlers:** companies that dismantle industrial facilities or infrastructure and are responsible for their waste management and disposal.
 - **Industrial End-users:** industries that use and/ or maintain equipment or infrastructure with parts made of composite materials, such as the transportation (airports, railway, shipping) and logistics sectors.
- **Academic Community:** researchers at universities and other research organisations working in the fields of materials science and engineering, composites, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling technologies, waste management, as well as other relevant disciplines (e.g. environmental sciences, social sciences, technical fields).
- **Technology and/or Innovation consultants:** organisations or individuals with expertise in technological and/ or commercial aspects of innovative technologies regarding sustainability and the circular economy.
- **Policy Makers:** decision-makers, EU and national level stakeholders, as well as the relevant standardisation and certification authorities, playing a key role in policy design, adoption and implementation, in the fields of the environment, waste management and circular economy.
- **Media/ Journalists or bloggers:** press or individual writers, specialised in relevant topics, such as new technologies and bioeconomy, waste management, circular economy.

2.2.2 The VIBES Stakeholders Board

The VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB) will include individuals, either independent or representing organisations, who are external to the consortium partners. It will be formed by a minimum number of 10 representatives, consisting of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings.

The members of the Stakeholders Board will be strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. They will collaborate in the project to effectively respond to market and social needs, give feedback and better guide decisions in the project. They will be industry-led, while fostering public and private collaboration.

The Stakeholders Board will complete the whole value chain together with consortium partner members and will be chaired by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN representative). Specific dissemination activities with the Stakeholders Board, including demonstration workshops and roundtables, will take place (see sections 4.3.2 and 4.3.3) to share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept effectively.

All partners can nominate individuals belonging to relevant stakeholder groups after initially conducting them informally, with the aim to be invited to participate in the Stakeholders Board.

After having received the initial informal interest and consent of the nominated individuals, the partners will then provide the following information to the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PAN), using an EXCEL file named “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” (see Annex 1):

- Stakeholder group/ sub-group that the nominated person belongs to (either chosen from the groups listed in the above Table 1 or by specifying another group/ sub-group)
- Contact name and gender of the nominated person
- Contact email
- Organisation (if applicable)
- Country
- Consortium partner (name/ organisation) that nominates them
- To be invited as Stakeholders Board member (yes/ no/ maybe)
- Any comments (i.e. specifying if they are member(s) of a relevant project or initiative, a relevant working group or cluster etc.)

Following their initial informal interest and consent, the nominated stakeholders will then be officially invited by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PAN) to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board by signing the “Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form” (Annex 2), after having read and agreed to the “Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference” (Annex 3) and the VIBES Privacy Policy (available on the VIBES website).

2.2.3 Synergies with Other Projects and Initiatives

Synergies within the EU bioeconomy and circular economy ecosystem, as well as complementary EU actions and regional/ national projects and initiatives, will be pursued by all partners in the VIBES research domains and industry sectors, to facilitate knowledge exchange, gain mutual dissemination benefits and exploit potential co-operations.

The following Table presents a list of indicative projects and initiatives that have been already identified as being related to VIBES, some more closely than others. This list may be updated during the course of the project, in collaboration with all project partners.

Table 2. Projects/ initiatives related to VIBES

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
Horizon2020 Project	BIZENTE	A biocatalytic model of enzymatic degradation as a novel alternative to the end-of-life (landfill and incineration) of thermoset composites.
Horizon2020 Project	ECOXY	Bio-based, recyclable, re-shapable & repairable (3R) fibre reinforced thermoset composites.

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
Horizon2020 Project	polynSPIRE	Demonstration of innovative technologies towards a more efficient and sustainable plastic recycling
LIFE Project	LIFE RECYSITE	Demonstrating recyclability and reuse of a new generation of high-performance fibre-reinforced thermoset composites from renewable resources (bio-waste).
Horizon2020 Project	HELACS	Holistic processes for the cost-effective and sustainable management of End of Life of Aircraft Composite Structures.
	BAMCO	Design of bio-composites from bamboo fibres and biobased resins, either thermoplastic or thermosets.
Horizon2020Project	LIBRE	Development and demonstration of the feasibility of lignin-based carbon fibre materials for application in energy and automotive sectors.
European Association	SPIRE	European Association, bringing together cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, minerals and ores, non-ferrous metals, pulp and paper, refining, steel and water sectors, several being world-leading sectors operating from Europe.
European Network	Vanguard Initiative	A unique alliance that gathers 39 of the most advanced industrial regions in Europe, focused on stimulating industrial innovation and building European value-chains based on complementarities in regional smart specialisation strategies.
European Network	CleanSky	Joint Undertaking of the European Commission and the European aeronautics industry, developing innovative, cutting-edge technologies aimed at reducing CO ₂ , gas emissions (particularly NO _x), and noise produced by aircraft.
European Network	Shift-to-Rail	European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation (R&I) and market-driven solutions by

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
		accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions.
European Network	EGVI	A contractual Public Private Partnership dedicated to delivering green vehicles and mobility system solutions of the future which match the major societal, environmental and economic challenges.
European Network	SusChem	European Technology Platform for Sustainable Chemistry. It is a forum that brings together industry, academia, policy makers and the wider society.
European Association	EuropaBio	Representing corporate and associate members across sectors, plus national and regional biotechnology associations which, in turn, represent over 2600 biotech companies, 2300 of which are SMEs.
European Association	European Bioplastics	Representing the interests of the thriving bioplastics industry in Europe.
European Association	EUBIA	European Biomass Industry Association, representing the interests of SMEs, Research Institutes and Universities working on the field of Biomass across Europe.

The actions required to create synergies with relevant projects and initiatives will be coordinated by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager with support from the rest of the consortium partners. Possible synergies may comprise of participation in events of similar projects and initiatives, dissemination of VIBES promotional material in events of similar projects and initiatives, invitations to participate in VIBES events, exchange of news through each other's channels, inclusion of the project's website and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects and initiatives, provision of feedback in each project's activities, etc. Synergies with certain projects will also include co-organisation of specific dissemination events, such as the demonstration workshops that will be organised in collaboration with some of the projects and initiatives mentioned in Table 2, as described in Chapter 4, section 4.3.2.

2.2.4 The VIBES Key Messages

It is very important for the VIBES Communication and Dissemination Strategy to define the fundamental messages of the project that will be communicated to the target audiences. A crucial point of the decided key messages is that they should give a clear image of the project's vision, but also they must be tailored depending on the needs of each target group (e.g. industrial developers and industrial users who would be

interested in the use of the VIBES developed materials and recycling technology, academics and scientists who would be interested in the scientific methods and results of VIBES and policy makers, the media and the general public, who are concerned about a greener economy and the protection of the environment.)

Although these messages will be specified as the project progresses, based on the actual data and outcomes and the milestones achieved, an initial list of key messages of the project that should be communicated to each stakeholder group, including the means to be used, is provided in the following Table as a point of reference.

Table 3. Key messages and means used for VIBES targeted stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
Industry (developers and users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability. • Contributing to reduced use of primary materials and landfilling. • Producing added-value products for the circular economy. • Facilitating the use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns. • Providing new knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Leaflets • Infographic • Articles in industry magazines • Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days • COMPOSIFORUM international events • Demonstration workshops • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Roundtables • Layman’s report • Final conference
Academic and research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing new knowledge and data on bio-based thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties. • Sharing new knowledge and data on recycling technology based on green pre-treatments. • Providing new knowledge and skills for European students in materials science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Scientific publications • Presentations in scientific conferences/ forums • COMPOSIFORUM international events

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Summer courses for younger generation of scientists • Final conference
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. • Boosting jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. • Achieving better results through collaborative innovation, contributing to competitiveness and helping meet social challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days • COMPOSIFORUM international events • Roundtables • Layman’s report • Final conference
Press General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrating an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling solution. • Returning products obtained from recycling process to the market. • Boosting jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. • Providing new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Press releases and articles • Spots in radio and TV programmes • Promotional videos • Layman’s report

If necessary, in the updated versions of the Communication, Dissemination and Training Report, these messages will be refined and more messages will be added based on the experience gained during the project. Note that in order to fulfil the project’s ambitions and claims, the above concepts/ messages must be communicated in their entirety.

2.2.5 The VIBES Key Assets

The VIBES project will have specific assets that can be of interest to different stakeholder groups, which will be disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective industrial users and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout. Although the VIBES assets will be defined in parallel to the unfolding of the project activities, a preliminary list of core assets is shown in the following Table. This list will evolve and be completed in the course of the project.

Table 4. VIBES main exploitable assets and outcomes (preliminary list)

VIBES main assets and outcomes
The VIBES 100% Biobased Bonding Materials , specific for epoxy, vinylester and polyester.
The VIBES 100% biobased resins and fibres to be used as new thermoset composite components.
The VIBES new thermoset composites with intrinsic recycling properties.
The VIBES new green recycling technology , resolving thermoset composites' end-of-life
The VIBES valorised resins (monomers/oligomers) and fibres , recovered from the recycling process, to be returned to the market as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks and by upcycling into new industrial products.
The VIBES industry-oriented protocols and manuals of new developed solutions, to be used for certification and authorisation of use.
The VIBES training course for industrial professionals on the circular economy for thermoset composites, to further develop the ideas and outcomes of VIBES.
The VIBES summer master classes for students on green composites, providing new knowledge and skills to the younger generation of scientists and engineers.
The VIBES brand and community of stakeholders , comprised of industrial developers and users of thermoset composite materials, the corresponding academic and research community, relevant technology & innovation experts, as well as policy makers, facilitating the dissemination and market uptake of VIBES results.

2.3 Role and Responsibilities

In order to achieve the aims and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, all members of the project consortium will play a key role during VIBES communication and dissemination activities. Partners' contribution will be a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones and progress will either involve communication and dissemination activities and engagement or turn into communication and dissemination assets. Furthermore, partners are expected to help with the online presence of VIBES by providing content for the project news published on the website and the project's Social Media accounts. This contribution can be anything, from a Twitter post to an article reflecting on a VIBES dissemination activity, with the goal of creating a constant flow of content regarding project's actions.

Finally, partners are welcome to pursue the widest possible exposure of the project through their participation in relevant events/conferences, articles and publications in online/offline sources of information (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.).

2.4 The Gender Dimension

The gender dimension has been integrated into the communication, dissemination and training strategy, including the establishment and monitoring of relevant indicators (see Table 14). Specific targets for the participation of women in certain communication, dissemination and training activities have been set, in order to guarantee gender balance and equality.

In particular, the gender dimension will be taken into consideration during the process of communicating with or selecting members and participants in various activities and events, as follows:

- In general, whenever possible, targeting communication and dissemination activities more intensely towards stakeholder groups that are represented by a fair number of female members.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board; at least 30% of its members are expected to be female.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when approaching academics and researchers, technicians, industrial professionals, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders, in order to invite them to participate in the project's relevant events (i.e. forums, workshops, roundtables, training programme and final conference); it is envisaged that at least 30% of the participants in such events will be female.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting the students for the summer training courses of the VIBES training programme, in which at least 30% of students are expected to be female.

3. Communication Means and Channels

Communication activities aim at increasing the public visibility of the project and its results using accessible language and suitable means and channels.

3.1 Visual Identity and Promotional Package

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) is in charge of the preparation of VIBES visual identity and the graphic design and content of the digital and printable promotional material of VIBES.

The promotional material of the project will be mainly used at the project's events, external events where partners will participate in and in the everyday publicity of the project.

3.1.1 Logo

By the end of the second month of the project, a project logo and visual identity were developed, in order to satisfy the visual and graphic requirements of the project. To achieve maximum visibility, the logo has the capability to make the project recognisable and will form the basis for the design of all the promotional material, which will be used for the different promotional and communication materials (e.g. leaflets, posters, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

The logo is represented on a friendly rounded font. The design involves the letter V which consists of 2 leaves; the green leaf refers to Green Solution and the purple leaf refers to Chemistry Innovation. The tag line connects the idea of Green Economy with that of Chemistry Innovation.

The logo colours (i.e. dark purple: #3C0F4B R: 60 / G: 15 / B:75 and light green: #23C887 R: 35 / G: 200 / B:135) are the colours of the project and should be used whenever possible to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.

The designed logo of VIBES, presented below with and without tag line, was adopted in agreement with all project partners.

Figure 1. VIBES logo with tag line

Figure 2. VIBES logo without tag line

Figure 3. The color codes of VIBES logo

In addition to the VIBES project logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc. produced in the frame of the project, the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) logo, combined with the Bio-based Industries Consortium logo and the Horizon2020 logo, will be shown.

Figure 4. The combined logo of Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking, Bio-based Industries Consortium and Horizon2020

The above combined logo will always be accompanied by the following statement: “This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190”.

3.1.2 Leaflets

Leaflets are important tools to support the communication and dissemination activities of VIBES project to attract the interest of stakeholders from the various target audiences.

By the end of the third month of the project, the first leaflet was produced in electronic and printable formats. It introduces the VIBES aim and goals, the project phases, the expected results and benefits.

A second leaflet summarising all project’s achievements will be produced in electronic and printable formats at the mid-end of the project so it can be distributed through partners’ networks and at relevant events.

The leaflets also provide information about the consortium partners and the type of stakeholders involved, together with contact and website details and acknowledge the funding that the project receives through the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme. The leaflets will be available in downloadable electronic format on the VIBES website. Furthermore, specifications on how to produce hard copies of the printable format of the leaflet will be given to all partners. Each partner will be responsible to produce the necessary number of printed copies of the leaflets to be available for

distribution at various events that will be organised in the frame of the project but also in external events, which partners will participate in.

The first leaflet of the project is illustrated below. The recommended specifications for producing hard copies of the printable format of the leaflet are as follows:

- Tri-Fold
- Dimensions: 14X29cm (42X29cm open)
- Paper: Velvet 250gr
- Mat Varnish

Figure 5. The first leaflet of VIBES

Aim

Develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, with the aim of decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

Project Goals

- Design and develop at least three 100% biobased bonding materials (BBM) for thermoset composites with tailored debonding functionalities.
- Design and develop at least three 100% biobased thermoset composite materials.
- Validate the thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties for optimum performance / cost ratio, in three high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.
- Design and implement a green recycling technology at pilot semi-industrial environment to separate and valorise the composite components as new feedstocks for the development of new products.
- Assess the life cycle impact of the developed products from environmental, social and economic point of view.
- Develop an exploitation & IPR strategy for Key Exploitable Results.
- Develop a Business Plan to demonstrate the commercial potential of the developed solution and describe how this potential will be realised.
- Inform, promote, communicate and disseminate the project objectives, activities and results; engage stakeholders to create synergies.
- Provide new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

Stakeholders

The VIBES project covers the whole composites value chain by taking into account, apart from the consortium partners, the Stakeholders Board and interaction with other projects of Biobased Industries through communication and dissemination activities:

- Industrial developers: thermoset composite developers, composite recyclers.
- Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users: aeronautical, naval, construction and energy industries; waste management; logistics and transport.
- Technology & innovation experts: academic / researchers; technology and innovation consultants.
- Impact multipliers: policy makers; media / journalists or bloggers.

3.1.3 Infographic

To add to the communication promotional package available for the communication activities of VIBES project, an infographic will be created by the end of the fifth month of the project. It will be in electronic format, following the same overall layout designed for the project, and will be available for downloading from the VIBES website. The infographic has the purpose of explaining the VIBES solution on recycling composites to a public audience and can be produced in poster or rollup formats. The infographic will be created for a general audience and can be used in stands or booths.

3.1.4 Promotional Videos

By the end of the fifth month of the project, a promotional video will be produced to raise awareness and to exploit viral effects. The video will be uploaded to the project's YouTube channel and the project's website and will be shared on the other Social Media Accounts. This short video will give an overview of the project, its objectives and present the main actions that will be developed during VIBES project.

A second promotional video will be produced at the end of the project, including the main project results and outcomes, and will be also uploaded to the project's YouTube channel and shared on the other Social Media Accounts.

Project Phases

Phase 1: Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)	Phase 2: Biobased Thermoset Composite Components	Phase 3: Inherent Recyclable Thermoset Composites	Phase 4: Recycling Technology Development	Phase 5: Sustainability and Commercial Exploitation
Three different approaches	Biobased substitutes for resins	Design and synthesis	Collection and direction to recycling	Sustainability and economical assessment
Exploring combinations and synergies	Biobased fibres and surface treatments	Technical validation tests	Handling, toxicity and safety evaluation	Aligning with Green Deal and climate neutral strategy
Upscaling best BBM	New fabrics for composite applications	Testing debonding treatments	Recycling technology design	Involvement of supply chain & EPR considerations
	Upscaling best composite components	Valorisation of recovered fractions	Pilot recycling plant	Exploitation & IPR management
		Upscaling into high added-value products		Building a business case
Phase 6: Communication, Dissemination and Training	Communication, dissemination and training plan.	Communication campaign and dissemination actions.	Stakeholders' engagement, creating synergies.	Providing knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

Benefits

- Improved properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability.
- Reduced use of primary materials and landfilling.
- Use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns.
- New knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials.
- New knowledge and skills for European students in material science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs.
- Increased jobs and turnover by promoting two new industrial sector interconnections in the newly created "Intrinsic Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain":
 - Interconnection between waste management and biotechnology sectors.
 - Interconnection between thermoset composites and biotechnology sectors.

www.vibesproject.eu

3.1.5 Document and Presentation Templates

With a view to design an easily recognisable graphical identity for the project, the following templates are being developed:

- Presentation template in PowerPoint, to be used as a basis for the various presentations created during the project, either for internal or external communication.
- Document template in MSWord, to be used as a basis for the project deliverables and reports.
- Letterhead template in MSWord, to be used for communication with project stakeholders and other written communication about the project.

These templates are shown in Annex 4.

3.1.6 Image Galleries

Image galleries will be used as visual promotional material in communication activities, for instance when posting news on the project website and social media or in project presentations and articles and the Layman's report. The image galleries include the following types of images:

- Pictures of VIBES related technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities.
- Images using the VIBES visual identity and colours including short promotional text and/ or relevant icons, mainly to be used when posting news on the project website and social media.
- Pictures or screenshots of project meetings, mainly to be used when posting relevant news on social media.

At this stage, an initial repository of images has been created, including pictures of relevant technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities, shared by several consortium partners. It is expected that during the course of the project, the consortium partners will continue to share relevant pictures of the various stages of the VIBES developed technologies and processes, showing the project progress.

3.2 VIBES Website

The project website (www.vibesproject.eu) is a key communication tool to increase the project visibility and impact, presenting the progress of the project to wider audiences. The VIBES website was launched in the fourth month of the project and serves as the online platform for public and consortium communication. The structure and content of the website have been designed to ensure ease of use and clearly reports the project's concept and objectives but will also contain relevant information about its progress, with news and event announcements.

Q-PLAN is the partner responsible for the design, development, maintenance, and management of the website. Special attention has been paid to a type of website that is responsive and accessible via and compatible with a variety of devices, including mobile devices.

Besides the key information presented, the project website will include all publishable project's outcomes, promotional material, reports, publications, deliverables and further resources of interest. The website will reflect the work happening in the context of VIBES. All partners are, hence, expected to contribute to the

content development process with news and updates. The website will regularly report on project's activities, internal and external events, findings, publishable outcomes, information about partners and similar projects/initiatives, as well as other news that are relevant to the project and its development.

The full structure and content of the VIBES website is presented in deliverable D6.1 "Project Website". The website sitemap is illustrated below:

- Home page
- About:
 - Concept and objectives
 - Consortium partners
 - Stakeholders
 - Activities
- Resources:
 - Reports
 - Publications
 - Training material
 - Promotional material
 - Other links (relevant events, relevant projects)
- News & Events:
 - Project developments
 - Dissemination and training events
 - Newsletters
 - Press Releases
- Contact us
- Privacy Policy
- Private area (link to MSTeams collaborative space for VIBES)

The above-mentioned points constitute a baseline for the website. The content and information posted on the website will be updated regularly, to be in line with the project's requirements and progress. The URL for the website is www.vibesproject.eu and the contact email for the project is in line with it (info@vibesproject.eu).

3.3 Social Media Accounts

The Social Media Accounts are valuable tools, which will act as one of the main pillars to promote the project and its ongoing activities. More specifically, a Twitter account, a LinkedIn account and a Facebook account were launched during the first month of the project, whereas a YouTube account was created during the third month of the project, aiming to build an online community of supporters and followers that will continue to exist beyond the duration of the project.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) will be responsible for the administration of VIBES social media accounts. However, all partners are expected to contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile).
- Promoting the accounts in their networks.

- Suggesting relevant profiles that VIBES should connect with.
- Promoting posts and news through the social media accounts of their own organisations.

Table 5. VIBES social media accounts

Social Media Platform	Name of Account	URL
Twitter	@VIBESEU2	https://twitter.com/VIBESEU2
LinkedIn	vibes-project	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vibes-project/
Facebook	VIBESProject2021	https://www.facebook.com/VIBESProject2021
YouTube	VIBES Project	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCauYtwBy8V47hLdnpzROZ8Q

The project’s social media will be regularly updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organisations / associations that promote activities and technologies relevant to VIBES, news from related EU projects etc.

The YouTube channel will be updated to include the first promotional video of VIBES that will be available to be published online in the fifth month of the project.

Screenshots of the VIBES presence on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube) are presented in Annex 5.

3.4 E-Newsletters

The project has committed to produce a bi-annual electronic newsletter (at least 8 in total), covering the activities developed every semester. The timing of the launch of each newsletter may be adapted to announce special events. The newsletter will be distributed to the project’s target audience, including all those who will subscribe to it via the project website, and it will be also uploaded to the website. The newsletter will summarise updates on the project’s developments and actions and will represent an alternative way to inform potential and/or existing followers with regards to the project’s concepts. Furthermore, the newsletter is a way to attract and retain stakeholders that are not familiar with social media or people who are not interested enough during the initial phases of the project, in order to keep them connected and try to engage them at a later stage.

The newsletters will be prepared by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager, with the contribution of all partners to specific content when necessary. Although the content of each newsletter will be agreed upon by the partners, the newsletter will mainly include the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the VIBES project
- Progress updates
- A project’s news section including articles that describe the main activities carried out during the last six months
- A section dedicated to future developments (e.g. upcoming events)

- A section listing other relevant major events
- Other types of relevant articles

The final newsletter will be accompanied by a feedback questionnaire for recipients to indicate the level of impact on them from information on project progress, achievements and recommendations.

3.5 Press Kit

3.5.1 Press Releases and Articles

At least six press releases will be produced on an ad-hoc basis, especially when achievements, progress and important actions are achieved or foreseen (i.e. an upcoming event). The press releases aim to inform stakeholders about the overall project actions and results, but they may also incorporate space for featuring specific stories related to project achievements in the form of short articles. General press releases will be developed, when necessary, targeting stakeholders at the EU level. Press releases may also be produced after each project meeting or prior to a project event with the purpose of attracting local media attention. For instance, the first press release was launched after the project kick-off meeting to announce the beginning of the project and introduce the project's goals and partners. The first press release is presented in Annex 6.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager will be in charge of the preparation of each press release, but every partner should translate it into their local language and send it to their local media.

3.5.2 Radio and TV Programmes

When findings are available, project partners will present the VIBES concept and progress in at least 2 radio or TV programmes, addressed to the general public. The project partners will identify such programmes in their local area, suitable for promoting innovative technological concepts in the fields of bioeconomy and circular economy. Initial contacts in TV, press and radio at regional (Aragón) and national level (Spain) have already been identified by the project coordinator (AITIIP), as shown in the following Table.

Table 6. TV, Press and Radio Channels at regional and national level (preliminary list)

Programme/ Section	Channel	Scope
Agujero de gusano	Aragón TV	Regional (Aragón)
Aragón en abierto	Aragón TV	Regional (Aragón)
Agrosfera	RTVE	National (Spain)
Tercer Milenio	Heraldo de Aragón (Press)	Regional (Aragón)
Agora	Aragón Radio	Regional (Aragón)

3.6 Articles in Press and Industry Magazines

In order for the project to reach a broader audience and make the VIBES known to its industrial stakeholders who belong to a wide range of industries and services, the partners are encouraged to submit their findings as articles in relevant magazines, both locally and internationally.

The following Table lists the first articles about VIBES, submitted by AITIIP in local press (Spain).

Table 7. AITIIP articles about VIBES in local press (Spain)

Date	Name of magazine/ newspaper	Type	Link
23/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/aragon/2021/06/23/vibes-un-proyecto-europeo-que-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion-1501499.html
23/6/2021	Mundoplast	Plastic sector	https://mundoplast.com/proyecto-vibes-reciclar-compuestos-termoestables/
23/06/2021	InterEmpresas	Business, focused on technology	https://www.interempresas.net/Nautica/Articulos/354671-AITIIP-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-aeronautica.html
24/06/2021	Química y Sociedad	Chemical sector	https://www.quimicaysociedad.org/aitiip-lidera-el-proyecto-vibes-que-desarrollara-una-tecnologia-ecologica-para-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-en-los-sectores-naval-aeronautico-y-construccion/
25/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	
26/06/2021	Retema	Environmental sector	https://www.retema.es/noticia/espana-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-tecnologia-para-reciclar-compuestos-plasticos
28/06/2021	Construible	Sustainable construction	https://www.construible.es/2021/06/28/vibes-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-polimeros-reutilizarlos-construccion

Date	Name of magazine/ newspaper	Type	Link
02/07/2021	Gestores de Recursos	Waste management	https://gestoresderesiduos.org/noticias/un-proyecto-europeo-con-participacion-espanola-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion
04/07/2021	Aragón Digital	General	https://www.aragondigital.es/2021/07/04/el-centro-tecnologico-aitiip-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-una-tecnologia-ecologica-de-reciclaje-de-piezas/
04/07/2021	Aragón Press	General	http://aragonpress.com/pages/notic/noticia.asp?notid=598423
07/07/2021	Diario de Teruel	General	https://www.diariodeteruel.es/teruel/el-aeropuerto-de-teruel-socio-en-un-proyecto-de-reciclaje-de-piezas-42551
04/08/2021	Tecnología Circular	Circular economy, technology and innovation	https://www.tecnologiadicircular.cl/2021/08/proyecto-europeo-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion/

In addition, the consortium has identified and listed a number of industry magazines, shown in the following Table, which are published internationally and are thematically close to the project. This list may be updated during the course of the project, in collaboration with all project partners.

Table 8. Selected industry magazines

No.	Name of Magazine	Description	Time of publication
1	European Biotechnology	A unique source of information about biotechnology in Europe's science and industry sectors.	4 times per year
2	Chemical & Engineering News	Its reporters and editors track important research advances, business and policy trends, chemical safety practices, career guidance, and more.	Weekly

No.	Name of Magazine	Description	Time of publication
3	European Plastics news	A business information platform for the European plastics industry.	Weekly
4	Composite World Magazine	A source for reliable news and information on what is happening in fibre-reinforced composites manufacturing.	Monthly
5	JEC Composites Magazine	The point of contact of the international Composite Community with topics covering scientific information, business, technology, manufacturing and application sectors trends.	6 times a year
6	Innovation in Textiles	Unique content, comment and features on new products, processes and technologies for all sectors of the global textiles industry, including composites.	4 times per year
7	Composites News International	Focused on Materials, Processes, Markets, Applications, Capacities, Supply and Demand.	Weekly
8	Construction & Demolition Recycling Association - Newsletter	Promoting and defending the environmentally sound recycling of the more than 583 million tons of recoverable construction and demolition (C&D) materials that are generated in the United States annually.	4 times a year
9	Aerotech News & Review	Serving the aerospace and defense industry of Southern California, Nevada and Arizona.	Biweekly/Fortnightly
10	Aircraft Maintenance Technology	Focused on the latest technology and maintenance best practices, as well as business trends and outlooks.	Every 3 months

No.	Name of Magazine	Description	Time of publication
11	Inside Industry	Reports on the latest technologies, acquisitions and mergers, and provides in depth profiles promoting companies and connecting them to new business opportunities.	N/A

3.7 Participation in Events/ Fairs/ Info-days

Participating in relevant events and fairs are unique opportunities to reach further audiences with a wide range of backgrounds. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners will participate in at least 6 external events and fairs with a view to:

- present VIBES concept,
- keep in touch with the latest advances,
- share knowledge,
- establish contacts and interactions with stakeholders,
- promote VIBES actions and results,
- raise awareness.

To ensure consistency in the presentation and communication of the project, partners will have at their disposal a common leaflet, a template for presentation slides, an infographic that can be produced as a poster or roll-out, and a template for publications, all of which will incorporate the VIBES logo and colours.

A number of relevant events, fairs and/ or info-days have been identified as potential events of interest for the VIBES consortium partners to participate, which are listed in the following Table. This list is indicative to offer guidance and assistance to the project partners and it is not exclusive. It may be updated during the course of the project, in collaboration with all project partners.

Table 9. Selected events and fairs

No.	Name of Fair	Description	Scheduled date	Location
1	BioSpain	The largest biotech event organised by a national bioindustry association in Europe.	27/09-01/10/2021	Spain
2	ECOMONDO	The reference event in Europe for the ecological transition and the new models of circular and regenerative economy.	26-29/10/ 2021	Rimini, Italy

No.	Name of Fair	Description	Scheduled date	Location
3	K-Trade-Fair	The world's largest trade fair for the plastics and rubber industry.	19-26/10/2022	Düsseldorf, Germany
4	Fakuma Show	Presents a united front for professionals in the plastic processing industry. It's an essential business platform geared towards procurement and professional partnerships.	12-16/10/2021	Friedrichshafen, Germany
5	AMI Composite Windows fair	The leading global trade fair for the process industry.	04-08/04/2022	Frankfurt, Germany
6	SIAE	The 54th edition of the Show will take place at the Le Bourget Parc des Expositions in 19-25 June 2023, and once again will bring together all the players in this global industry around the latest technological innovations.	19-25/06/2023	Le Bourget Parc des Expositions
7	FARNBOROUGH air show	The Farnborough International Air show is an internationally recognised bi-annual event where the entire aviation and aerospace industry gathers to learn, network and do business.	18-22/07/2022	Farnborough International Exhibition and Conference Centre
8	Composites for Europe	A trade fair and industry forum for all professions with a connection to composites as well as corresponding technology and applications.	09-11/11/2021	Stuttgart Trade Fair Centre
9	Expoquimia	Connecting science and industry to help bring major projects to fruition. Expoquimia is opening up to the outside world in an increasingly globalized scenario, with a view to the new Horizon 20/20 initiative and offering the market new business opportunities.	N/A	GRAN VIA VENUE

No.	Name of Fair	Description	Scheduled date	Location
10	The Greener Manufacturing Show	Event for any sustainability-focused company looking to design and manufacture their products from more sustainable materials, limit and eliminate the use of toxic chemicals, and reduce the impact of their industrial and manufacturing processes on the environment and global climate change.	10-11/11/2021	Cologne, Germany
11	ITMA	The world's largest international textile and garment technology exhibition, ITMA highlights innovations that will help textile and garment manufacturers transform and grow their business.	8-14/06/2023	Milan Italy
12	European Bioplastics Conference	Leading business and discussion forum in Europe for the global bioplastics sector.	30/11/2021 – 1/12/2021	Berlin, Germany

The following Table lists the first events in which VIBES was presented by AITIIP in Spain, even before the official beginning of the project.

Table 10. AITIIP presentation of VIBES to relevant events (Spain)

Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
25/09/2020	Online pitch event/ Presentation to Isover-Saint Gobain	Industry	Spain
29/09/2020	Online pitch event/ Presentation to VEOLIA (Water, waste and energy management services)	Industry	Spain
26/03/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation to Grupo Antolín (car sector supplier)	Industry	Spain
16/04/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation to Suez	Industry	Spain

Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
20/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation to EDA (European Defence Agency)	Industry	Spain
25/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation to Finsa (Wood transformation company)	Industry	Spain
29/06/2021	Workshop on bridging the gap between academia and industry: training in European digitalization and circular economy projects/ Presentation of the project at Spanish Industry (CAAR)	Industry	Spain

3.8 Layman’s Report

The Layman’s report will be produced as a final report of the VIBES project, summarising the work of the project for a general audience. It will serve as a valuable marketing tool for promoting the environmental and economic benefits of the project results and extending the impact of the project beyond the area of implementation. It will clearly outline the achievements of the project and its long-term environmental and economic benefits to attract the interest of journalists and policymakers, along with those experts and stakeholders focusing on similar issues to those addressed by the project.

The Layman’s report will include the following information:

- The problem, introducing one or two paragraphs on the background to the project.
- Project overview, introducing the project's specific objectives, the benefits of the innovative solution (environmental, cost-benefit), the partners involved, as well as the project duration and budget.
- Results, introducing the innovative solution in a non-technical way; this would be the core part of the report, describing the innovative solutions brought to the market thanks to the project.
- The market, introducing the target users and customers.
- The European added value, introducing the benefits at EU level.
- Contact information, including e-mail and website.

The Layman’s report will be between 5 and 10 pages in length, produced in electronic format. It will be presented in an attractive way, using eye-catching images where possible and presenting results in an easy-to-read way, such as tables, charts, and boxes.

3.9 Internal Communication

Daily communication between partners will be done through email. Exchange of detailed information between Work Packages will be done also through email and by meetings.

To facilitate communication, the following emailing lists have been established.

Table 11. Internal mailing lists

LIST	MEMBERS
vibes_all@vibesproject.eu	It includes every participating member of VIBES consortium
vibes_technical@vibesproject.eu	It includes every member of VIBES consortium who is responsible for technical issues
vibes_administration@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for administrative issues
vibes_dissemination@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for the dissemination of the project

4. Dissemination Means and Channels

Dissemination activities aim at making the project results available to the scientific community, policy makers and industry, using scientific language and accurate statements.

4.1 Scientific Publications

It is an obligation and of interest to the consortium to widely disseminate the proposed new materials and technologies through qualified scientific publications. Scientific publications and conferences are important dissemination channels for sharing VIBES outcomes to academic and industrial target communities, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the results in their own work. It is expected that academic and research partners will take up the leading role in drafting scientific articles, assisted by all relevant consortium members. At least 6 scientific publications are foreseen, including at least 4 articles in scientific journals and at least 2 posters in scientific conferences.

An indicative list of journals for the dissemination of scientific outputs is given in the following Table. This list may be updated during the course of the project, in collaboration with all project partners.

Table 12. Selected scientific/ technical journals

No.	Name of Journal	Description	Publication Period
1	Green Chemistry, Royal Society of Chemistry	It provides publications of innovative research on the development of alternative green and sustainable technologies.	24 issues per year
2	International Journal of Biological Macromolecules	An established international journal of research into chemical and biological aspects of all natural macromolecules, presenting the latest findings of studies on the molecular structure and properties of proteins, macromolecular carbohydrates, glycoproteins, proteoglycans, lignins, biological poly-acids, and nucleic acids.	28-30 issues per year
3	Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing	Original research papers, review articles, case studies, short communications and letters from a wide variety of sources dealing with all aspects of the science and technology of composite materials, including fibrous and particulate reinforcements in polymeric, metallic and ceramic matrices, and 'natural' composites such as wood and biological materials.	12 issues per year

No.	Name of Journal	Description	Publication Period
4	Composites Part B: Engineering	It publishes impactful research of high quality on composite materials, supported by fundamental mechanics and materials science and engineering approaches.	24 issues per year
5	Composites Science and Technology	It publishes refereed original articles on the fundamental and applied science of composites, focusing on polymeric matrix composites with reinforcements/fillers ranging from nano- to macro-scale.	16 issues per year
6	Composite Structures	It publishes papers which contribute to knowledge in the use of composite materials in engineering structures.	24 issues per year
7	New Biotechnology	It covers both the science of biotechnology and its surrounding political, business and financial milieu.	Bimonthly
8	Chemical Engineering	It focuses upon: chemical reaction engineering, environmental chemical engineering, and materials synthesis and processing.	Bimonthly
9	RSC Advances	It publishes advances in chemistry, and in topics of interest to the chemistry community.	Irregular (70+/year)
10	Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering ACS Publications	It covers research in green chemistry, green engineering, biomass, alternative energy, and life cycle assessment.	Weekly
11	Organic Process Research & Development	It reports original work from the broad field of industrial process chemistry but also presents academic results that are relevant, or potentially relevant, to industrial applications.	Monthly
12	International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives	The International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives draws together the many aspects of the science and technology of adhesive materials, from fundamental research and development work to industrial applications.	Bimonthly

No.	Name of Journal	Description	Publication Period
13	Journal of Polymer Science	It has served the community as a forum for fundamental research on synthesis, chemistry, physics, and engineering of polymers.	Twice per year
14	Textile Research Journal	It introduces new concepts, innovative technologies, and improved understanding of textile materials, processes, chemistry and systems.	20 issues per year
15	Applied Polymer Materials	The journal is devoted to reports of new and original experimental and theoretical research of an applied nature that integrates fundamental knowledge in the areas of materials, engineering, physics, bioscience, polymer science and chemistry into important polymer applications.	Monthly
16	Applied Polymer Science	The journal covers all applications of polymers, including membranes, energy conversion and storage, and biomedical implants; as well as all types of polymeric materials, from polysaccharides, to composites, to biodegradable polymers.	Bimonthly
17	Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites	The Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites (JRP) occasionally publishes special issues, which are usually selected from international conferences.	Biweekly
18	Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety	The scope of the journal covers three main the following themes: Ecotoxicology, Environmental Chemistry and Environmental Safety.	Monthly
19	Resources, Conservation & Recycling	It emphasizes the transformation processes involved in a transition toward more sustainable production and consumption systems.	Monthly

4.2 Participation in Scientific Conferences

Participating in scientific conferences is a unique opportunity to reach audiences with various scientific and industrial backgrounds that are relevant to VIBES. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners will participate in at least 3 scientific conferences in which VIBES results will be presented to relevant international scientific forums.

An indicative list of scientific conferences and relevant events that have already been identified is provided in the following Table. This list may be updated during the course of the project, in collaboration with all project partners.

Table 13. Selected conferences & events

No.	Name of Conference	Description	Next Scheduled Date	Location
1	International Conference on Manufacturing of Advanced Composites (IMAC)	A forum for academia and industry to share ideas and approaches, showcasing world-leading manufacturing research for advanced composites, recognising and responding to industry needs.	20-22/10/2021	Virtual: Online
2	International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM)	The premier international conference in the field of composite materials, attracting leading researchers and practitioners, to report and exchange ideas on the latest developments in the advancement and exploitation of a wide range of composite materials and structures.	30/07 – 04/08/2023	Belfast, Northern Ireland
3	ECP European Chemistry Partnering	It has the mission to bring international creative people from all points of chemical production and value creation into exchange, across genders, disciplines, regions, cultures, countries and continents.	17/02/2022	Frankfurt, Germany
4	EFIB, European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology and the Bioeconomy	It is the market leading annual event in Europe for Industrial Biotechnology and the Bioeconomy, where delegates are provided with an update on the	06-07/10/2021	Vienna, Austria

No.	Name of Conference	Description	Next Scheduled Date	Location
		status and outlook of biobased industries.		
5	ESIB European Summit of Industrial Biotechnology	An event that not only covers science but also deals with industrial needs and hopes, economic demands, funding resources or political aspirations and leaves space for networking and recreation.	14-17/11/2022	Graz, Austria
6	BIOPOL International Conference on Biodegradable Polymers and Sustainable Composites	The conference has the aim to provide a forum to exchange up-to-date ideas and opinions on current research and new applications of biopolymers and bio-composites.	N/A	N/A
7	COMPOSIFORUM Composite forum for industry and researchers	The international industrial forum about composites and their applications.	N/A	N/A
8	MRO Europe Aviation Week Conference	It is the premier event in this region for the commercial air transport maintenance, repair and overhaul industry.	Conference: 19-21/10/2021 Exhibition: 20-21/10/2021	RAI, Amsterdam
9	ISGC (International Symposium on Green Chemistry)	It gathers the most eminent scientists involved in the field of green chemistry to debate on the future challenges of Chemistry keeping in mind the problems of access to a sustainable energy, the management of resources (carbon, water, metals, minerals), human development, global warming, impact on the environment and competitiveness of the Industry.	16-20/05/2022	La Rochelle, France

No.	Name of Conference	Description	Next Scheduled Date	Location
10	MACRO World Polymer Congress	The programme comprises 9 themes representing fields such as polymers for biomedical engineering, nanotechnology, physics and engineering.	17-21/07/2022	Manitoba, Canada
11	EPF, European Polymer Congress	The event has become one of the largest polymer science conferences in the world.	26/06-01/07/2022	Prague, Czech Republic
12	Composites Recycling Conference – JEC Group	It is the only global trade show dedicated to composite materials and applications.	08-12/03/2022	Paris, France
13	ECB – European Congress on Biotechnology	In 2022, the Congress will be a joint event with the theme “Biotechnology for the Grand Challenges of our Society”, sponsored by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) and European Federation of Biotechnology (EFB)..	22-25/05/2022	Maastricht, The Netherlands

4.3 Organisation of Events

In the frame of VIBES, several events will be organised to serve the project’s objectives and promote the project and its outcomes. In more detail, the following types of events are scheduled as part of the project’s dissemination plan.

4.3.1 COMPOSIFORUM International Events

COMPOSIFORUM is the “Composites Forum for the Industry and Researchers”, organised by AITIIP in collaboration with the University of Zaragoza, as part of the AITIIP Chair (AITIIP CATEDRA) that advises and defines the strategic lines of Research, Development and Innovation projects of mutual interest between the University of Zaragoza and AITIIP foundation.

COMPOSIFORUM gathers experts in plastic composites and takes place every two years (next editions will be in 2022 and 2024). A lecture slot will be reserved specifically for the dissemination of the VIBES project in both next editions of COMPOSIFORUM. The summit is subjected to COVID mobility allowance.

4.3.2 Demonstration Workshops

Three demonstration workshops will be organised, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept. The VIBES Stakeholders Board will help to articulate and lead this activity.

- One workshop will be dedicated to Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and material certification -ISCC as well as the policies required to regulate the use of VIBES products and technology to reach the market and the society. This workshop will be organised under the lead of ECODES, an independent non-profit organisation based in Zaragoza (Spain) that works towards sustainable and environmentally friendly development and will be represented in the VIBES Stakeholders Board. This workshop will be organised during the fourth year of the project.

Figure 6. Demonstration workshop in PLATA

- One 5-hour workshop was organised together with HELACS project and focused on dismantling, collecting, sorting and directing processes and composites waste manipulation. This workshop took place on 29th July, 2021 at PLATA premises in Teruel (Spain) with the participation of Airbus, PLATA and AITIIP. There were 12 participants (33% female) from the aeronautic sector, technology providers, dismantling and recycling companies. During the workshop different aspects of VIBES and HELACS, advanced materials, efficient manufacturing, circular economy and digitalisation were treated with the aim of gathering feedback and engagement.

The event allowed us to confirm that the objectives of VIBES are aligned to industry and stakeholders. They are interested in the results and think that they will be useful in their future processes. They also expressed their intention to participate actively in project’s activities and in future initiatives.

Figure 7. Demonstration workshop in CIRCE

- One 2-hour workshop was organised together with BIZENTE, polynSPIRE and LIFE RECYSITE projects on dealing with properties, industrial applications and end-of-life alternatives of thermoset composites. This workshop took place on 2nd July, 2021 at CIRCE premises in Zaragoza (Spain) with the aim of establishing synergies and interactions with polynSPIRE project. There were 6 participants (20% female) from research and innovation centres. The workshop included a technical discussion about

polyamide degradation processes and a visit to the lab in which the microwave solvolysis processes take place, which served as feedback for the green solvolysis process developed in VIBES. The event allowed us to confirm the alignment of the VIBES objectives to current research lines and the interest of the scientific community in its results.

4.3.3 Roundtables

In addition to the workshops mentioned above, two roundtables will be organised by Q-PLAN as part of the VIBES Stakeholders Board activities. The roundtables will be organised at key turning points of the VIBES project, hosting the VIBES Stakeholders Board with the participation of project partners, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. The social changes and impact that VIBES may have in the society will be also explored.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) will collect feedback from the activities of the VIBES Stakeholders Board and will present them in a final deliverable D6.6 “Feedback on key points from stakeholders’ panel activities” by the end of the project.

4.3.4 Final Conference

By the end of the project, the VIBES final conference will take place. All project partners will participate in the organisation of this event under the lead of one of the partners, to be decided when considering the highest impact to be achieved. The aim of the conference will be to spread the accumulated knowledge and exploitation strategies and present the final achievements to scientists, industry, policy makers and generally to all interested parties, with a view to fostering industrial and research utilisation of the project results, as well as contribution to standards. Major stakeholders will be invited to participate in this event, including also all the students taking part in the VIBES training programme, described in Chapter 5. During the final conference, a certificate will be handed to those having finalised the summer training course and the open e-learning version of the VIBES training programme, as described in Chapter 5, sections 5.4.2 and 5.4.3. Keynote speakers will be invited to attract more public audience and the industrial and scientific community.

The VIBES partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks. All activities implemented towards the organisation of this conference will be reported in the fourth and final version of deliverable D6.5 “Report on communication, dissemination and training activities – Update 3”.

5. Training Programme

A training programme will be aligned with the communication and dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders of the VIBES project and to science and engineering students. The Training programme in the project represents the strategic vision of the Consortium in view of sharing and therefore implementing the open knowledge that will be gathered and generated within the project, both by the science students and by professionals in varied industrial sectors.

The training activities will also contribute to the dissemination and therefore exploitation of the project results, contributing to raising awareness and providing novel competencies in the current and next generation of professionals.

The Project Coordinator (AITIIP) will be responsible for designing, planning and organising the training programme, producing the deliverable D7.6 “Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals”.

5.1 Training strategy

Training activities contribute to professional development, through advanced training of researchers and other key staff, science students, industry staff, and in general potential users of the knowledge generated by the project.

The complementary expertise of the partners within the project will have a positive effect in generating cross-collaboration, a better capacity for training of young researchers and eventually fruitful staff exchange (e.g. between academia and enterprises).

The specific targets of the training activities are:

- **transfer** of knowledge within the participants including students, researchers and industrial staff.
- **spreading** of knowledge from both the academic and industrial professional within the project to researchers and students and to industrial staff outside the consortium, promoting S&T cohesion within the European research goals and so increase skills across Europe
- raising **awareness** of key stakeholders who are essential to successful exploitation and commercialization of the novel technology and products developed.

The approach used in the project is based on Open Science, focused on open dissemination and open materials.

It is generally accepted that Open Science leads to increased impact associated with wider sharing and re-use and could increase trust in science and in the reliability of scientific results.

In 2014, a core set of principles were drafted in order to optimise the reusability of research data, named the FAIR Data Principles. They represent a community-developed set of guidelines and best practices to ensure that data or any digital object are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable. We will use this concept in our training design:

- **Findable:** The first thing to be in place to make data reusable is the possibility to find them. In VIBES cases, the training will be available through web and e-learning platform (aitemy learning)
- **Accessible:** The data should be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised and open protocol that guarantee a simple access. In this sense, the e-learning platform used, is intuitive and user-friendly.
- **Interoperable:** The data should be able to be combined with and used with other data or tools.
- **Re-usable:** Ultimately, FAIR aims at optimizing the reuse of data. In this sense, VIBES will create OERs (Open Education Resources) that could be used by other teachers and learners.

5.2 Objectives, Target Audiences and Themes

The training programme will be designed and implemented with the aim of providing knowledge and skills on the topic of new recycling technologies for composite materials and the circular economy as well as to present and transfer the knowledge and results acquired during the project.

The training programme will be promoted among the VIBES stakeholders that are included in the VIBES stakeholders’ database as well as Universities and Education Centres and other relevant contacts of the consortium partners. The stakeholders’ database will be created by sharing relevant contacts and information among project partners using the “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” form (see Annex 1).

In particular, the training programme will focus on the following types of stakeholders:

- Researchers from academia and technicians related to VIBES interconnected sectors (materials science, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling and waste management)
- Industrial professionals who may potentially collaborate with and/ or be involved in the business that VIBES key exploitable results will generate (industrial developers, converters, dismantlers, waste managers and end-users).
- Science and engineering students (fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry), with the aim of creating a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.
- Anyone in the open society who is interested in the subject of green technologies and circular economy.

VIBES training is focused on some specific themes:

- Design and development of biobased materials
- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

VIBES will validate a better use of resources demonstrating the high potential of the Circular Economy to implement a resilient energy union with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation will be based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology based on the development of smart BBM for the first time applied to composite thermoset plastic) which will equip to Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor and will this knowledge to design and implement the training activities.

5.3 Training Methodology

The training activities will be held in a variety of formats and methods, both in presence - workshops, technological breakfast and face to face courses - and remotely - online training. Certificates of attendance are envisaged for all the training sessions, both online and in presence after completing a test.

5.3.1 Face to face training sessions

It is recommended that the training events occurring in presence should be organised before, after, or alongside big community events, so as to build synergies, facilitate participation and maximise the impact of the training activities.

Venues for the training events should be selected carefully and minimum requirements will be the availability of hardware (projectors/wide screens) and internet connection that will allow for interactive activities to engage the audience and of course to guarantee the necessary security of the audience (COVID pandemic is an example).

The training events will be well-planned and announced far in advance, at least 3 months before the event takes place, to promote them within the relevant audience and to increase the participation.

The training events will be organised in Spain and Ireland; to increase the engagement, local language is highly recommended for the national events.

Events occurring in presence allow for higher involvement of the audience and longer sessions of training that may deepen the participants' knowledge on specific topics addressed by the event. These events should be possibly co-organised with other projects in the task force, especially if co-located with some important event/conference.

5.3.2 Online training sessions

The advantage of online training is the wider coverage and the possibility to re-play and learn following a personal path and rhythm. Remote sessions however are usually less interactive and do not allow for a profound discussion of the thematic covered by the event.

In this case, the online training will be a recording of the summer course. It will be announced and the corresponding material (presentation and recording) will be made available to the public on **aitemy learning platform** (<https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>) and though a link on VIBES website.

The online learning content will allow trainees to undertake the course at their own convenience. Course material will be offered via recorded video and presentation slides. Upon completion of the course, the AITIIP can release certificates to those who passed the requirements.

A link will be integrated with the VIBES website, allowing it to further become the single point of reference for VIBES trainees.

5.3.3 Evaluation

The test could be a multiple choice, true or false and can be automatically checked. Another option for the test/exam in the face-to face events could be to submit a practical exam and a trainer would manually check and grade the trainees.

5.4 Training activities

The training will be articulated around the following channels.

1. Research workshops for researchers and technicians
2. Summer course for students, organised through the CATEDRA AITIIP and replicated at the University of Limerick summer school.
3. Free access to training material, generated by the summer course, through AITIIP e-learning platform (AITEMY), open for both students and society.
4. Technological breakfast and workshops at AITIIP facilities for industrial professionals, in collaboration with the Chamber of Commerce of Zaragoza.

In each course or workshop special care will be taken so that there is a gender equality among participants, a balance between male and female participants.

VIBES TRAINING ACTIVITIES

5.4.1 Research Workshops for researchers and technicians

Three research-oriented workshops will be organised for researchers and technicians, in collaboration with ARAID (Aragonese Research and Development Foundation for the Recruitment of Regional Talent) and will gather researchers from academia and industry related to VIBES interconnected sectors.

These workshops focus on researchers and technicians' profiles mainly coming from Aragón and Spain but the activities organised by ARAID are open to all countries. The three workshops will be organised following key milestones of the project, with the aim of transferring knowledge and gather feedback from peers. Tentatively, the research workshops will be organized in month 24 after WP1 and WP2 results are delivered, month 37 after WP3 results are delivered and at the end of the project.

AITIIP will contact ARAID in the following months in order to define the best format (duration, type of content, presenters, modality and language) for these workshops. It is expected that the partners responsible for the VIBES results take part as content developers and presenters.

5.4.2 Summer Training Course

The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum will include latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project. The VIBES consortium partners will prepare the content of the training and teach the relevant topics. Additional learning or expertise will not be required.

The contents of the course will be:

- Design and development of biobased materials

- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

Under the coordination of AITIIP, the partners will start to collaborate in the creation of the contents from the 12th month of the project when the first results will be available. The course will be carried out during the summer of 2024 for a group of 30 students. An evaluation will be done at the end of the course and an additional evaluation will be done 6 months later.

The summer course will be organised in Teruel Campus, a rural area in south Aragon region that belongs to the University of Zaragoza and located next to PLATA facilities which will be visited in order to familiarise future employees with the industry environment of vision, problem identification and solution implementation from the circular economy perspective.

The summer course will be organised within the framework of CATEDRA AITIIP, a contractual agreement with the University of Zaragoza, which is renewed every year, financing activities related to formation and research.

The above Summer Course will be replicated in the summer programme of the University of Limerick.

The visit to PLATA facilities will be also proposed to be replicated by ACCIONA and IDEC in their own premises.

In both cases, the course will be in English to facilitate its implementation in each facility and encourage the participation of other students from any EU member-state.

In parallel to the above training, AITIIP and University of Limerick will extend the research results generated by the project by launching at least 3 MSc theses and 2 PhD theses.

5.4.3 E-learning

In order to ensure open access to the developed content and maximise the returns to society, the summer course will be recorded. An open version for a wider student audience and the society in general will be uploaded and made free for use through AITIIP e-learning platform, AITEMY: <https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>.

The e-learning content will be available once the summer courses in Teruel and Limerick have taken place. The students will have to pass a quiz in the platform to check their performance.

The e-learning content is expected to reach at least 100 students and other stakeholders interested in the technological areas related to the VIBES project.

5.4.4 Training for Industrial Professionals

The training for industrial professionals will be organised by AITIIP in collaboration with the Chamber of Commerce of Zaragoza, one of AITIIP's patronage.

The innovation committee of the Chamber of Commerce of Zaragoza will collaborate in the organisation of one technological breakfast for industrial professionals in the fields addressed by the VIBES project. At least 40 Spanish industrial professionals will take part in the event. International experts would be invited. The language of the event will be Spanish.

In addition, one workshop for industrial professionals will be organised at AITIIP facilities about eco-design using biobased materials. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish, but the possibility to organise it in English will be evaluated if there is an interest from European industrial professionals to take part. The contents will be created by the VIBES consortium partners and will be taught by AITIIP in collaboration with other partners. In order to maximise its impact, this workshop will be organised together with the COMPOSIFORUM event whenever possible.

Furthermore, professional visits to VIBES industrial partners (IDEC, ACCIONA and PLATA) will be also organised for potential stakeholders and will be open to industrial collaborators interested in the fields addressed by the VIBES project.

5.5 Training activities calendar

#	Date (tentatively)	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
1	M24	Spain	Workshop	Workshop focusing on researchers and technicians' profiles mainly coming from Aragón and Spain, organised by ARAID	Academia, industry
2	M24	Spain	Workshop	Workshop focusing on researchers and technicians' profiles mainly coming from Aragón and Spain, organised by ARAID	Academia, industry
3	M37	Spain	Workshop	Workshop focusing on researchers and technicians' profiles mainly coming from Aragón and Spain, organised by ARAID	Academia, industry
4	M37	Spain	Course	Summer school course. The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum will include latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project.	Academia, industry, open society
5	M37	Ireland	Course	Summer school course. The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum will include	Academia, industry, open society

#	Date (tentatively)	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
				latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project.	
6	M40	Online (aitemy platform)	Course	Recording of the summer school course.	Academia, industry, open society
7	M44	Spain	Lecture/seminar	The innovation committee of the Chamber of Commerce of Zaragoza will collaborate in the organisation of one technological breakfast for industrial professionals in the fields addressed by the VIBES project. International experts would be invited. The language of the event will be Spanish.	Industry
8	M46	Spain	Workshop	Workshop for industrial professionals will be organised at ATIIP facilities about eco-design using biobased materials. The duration will be half day. The language of the workshop will be Spanish.	Industry

VIBES		Last updated: 30/9/2021																																																											
		2021												2022												2023												2024												2025											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May							
		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48												
WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Training																																																													
T6.3- Dissemination activities																																																													
Scientific publications																																																													
Participation in scientific conferences																																																													
COMPOSIFORUM international events																																																													
Demonstration workshops																																																													
Roundtables																																																													
Final Conference																																																													
Feedback on key points from stakeholders' panel activities																																																													
T6.4- Training activities																																																													
Research workshops																																																													
Summer training course																																																													
E-learning																																																													
Training for industrial professionals																																																													
Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals																																																													

7. Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting

7.1 Performance Indicators and Monitoring

The implementation of communication and dissemination strategy will be monitored on an on-going basis according to the level of realisation of the communication and dissemination objectives and outcomes that have been set up. The frequent evaluation of communication and dissemination activities will allow to monitor and measure their impact and, if necessary, adapt them in order to increase the project’s visibility and awareness. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager has the overall responsibility of the monitoring and evaluation of VIBES communication and dissemination activities, although the project partners are also expected to help by continuously monitoring and evaluating the publicity and communication activities they carry out.

Analytical measures and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used in order to monitor the implementation and assess the impact of communication, dissemination and training activities. A number of metrics employed for the monitoring and evaluation of these activities are provided in the following Table, together with their target values. However, **these targets might be later adapted** based on the experience gathered or additional metrics may be also included. All these metrics will be documented in the updated version of the dissemination and communication plan (Month 18). Besides the quantitative metrics indicated below, qualitative data will be also gathered by eliciting feedback from stakeholders, on all occasions that allow direct contact with them (e.g. events organised or attended).

Table 14. KPIs and target values

KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status
Number of Stakeholders Board Members	At least 10 (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of project leaflets designed	2 (one in the beginning and another at the mid-end)	1

¹ The essential KPIs for monitoring the implementation of the communication, dissemination and training activities are marked in bold; they are those with target values that are specific and not indicative (specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). The rest of the KPIs are for assessing the impact of the communication, dissemination and training activities; they are considered as equally important, but their target values are indicative at this stage and may be later adapted based on the experience gathered.

Number of project infographics designed	1	N/A
Number of project videos produced	2 (one in the beginning and one at the end)	1
Number of e-newsletters	8 (2 per year, covering the activities developed every semester)	N/A
Number of press releases (in English)	At least 6	1
Number of radio or TV programmes that VIBES was communicated to	2	N/A
Number of articles published in industry magazines	At least 4	N/A
Number of events /fairs/ info-days in which partners participated	At least 6	7
Number of distributed promotional materials	2,000 copies of leaflets distributed in project/external events (indicative)	N/A
Number of visits to the VIBES website	15,000 unique visitors by the end of the project (indicative)	N/A
Number of followers in the social media accounts	2,000 followers (indicative) (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube)	114
Number of subscribers to e-newsletters	500 (indicative)	N/A
Number of scientific papers published	At least 6 (at least 4 articles in scientific journals and 2 posters in conferences)	N/A
Number of scientific conferences in which partners participated	At least 3	N/A
Number of COMPOSIFORUM international events organised	At least 2	N/A

Number of participants in COMPOSIFORUM international events	100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of demonstration workshops organised for industry and stakeholders	3	2
Number of organised roundtables	2	N/A
Number of participants in the Final Conference	At least 100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of summer training courses, organised as part of the training programme	2	N/A
Number of participants in the summer training courses	30 students per course (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of participants on e-learning platform: AITEMY	At least 100 students (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of research-oriented workshops organised for technicians and professionals from academia and industry, as part of the training programme	3	N/A
Number of training activities for industrial professionals, organised as part of the training programme	2 (one technological breakfast and one workshop)	N/A
Number of professionals (academia and industry) participated in training (research-oriented, technological breakfast, workshop)	At least 100 (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	N/A
Number of MSc theses launched	3	N/A
Number of PhD theses launched	2	N/A

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to intensify the communication and dissemination actions in the forthcoming months, putting emphasis on the production of scientific publications, the attendance of external conferences and events as well as the improvement of website visitors and social media followers.

7.2 Reporting

Communication and dissemination reporting is essential for keeping track of all the communication and dissemination activities that were carried out. Therefore, the project partners are expected to continuously report all their relevant activities on a six-months periodic report and to contribute to the continuous monitoring of VIBES communication and dissemination activities.

In order to facilitate the reporting of each communication and dissemination activity undertaken, three reporting tools have been designed and shared with all partners, as shown in the following Table.

Table 15. Reporting tools for monitoring the communication and dissemination activities

Annex	Reporting Tool	Coverage	When
7	Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template	All communication and dissemination activities, which partners were involved in during every 6 months period.	Every 6 months
8	Event Reporting Form	Every single event organised or event in which partners participated.	Within 30 days following the completion of the event
9	External Conferences and Events Template	Any external conference/ event identified by partners, which is considered relevant to VIBES and beneficial to attend.	Throughout the project

7.2.1 Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

During each project semester, all partners are expected to complete the “Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template” (Annex 7) reporting all communication and dissemination activities that they carried out during the previous six months.

It is an Excel file that should be sent at the end of each project semester to Q-PLAN. All the information required must be provided. The European Commission collects all these data from the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN). Therefore, for each activity each partner should indicate the following information:

- Date
- Place
- Type of activity
- Title
- Type of audience
- Size of audience per type of stakeholder group

- Countries addressed
- Organisation's role
- Type and quantity of project promotional materials used (e.g. number of leaflets distributed, number of project presentations)
- Other partners or external organisations involved
- Short description of activity
- Other comments (if relevant)
- Relevant contacts made (if relevant)

7.2.2 Event Reporting Form

For each completed event (workshop, conference, etc.), partners are required to complete the “Event Reporting Form” (Annex 8) providing information regarding the event that they were involved in. This form should be sent to Q-PLAN within 30 days after the end of the event and the event should also be communicated to Q-PLAN, in advance, for promotional purposes.

It is a structured document that includes the following information:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendees including % of female attendees, duration)
- Goals and relevance to the project
- Organisation of the event (if applicable)
- Dissemination activities within the event
- Structure of the event
- Outcomes of the event
- Evaluation of the event
- Annexes (list of participants, agenda, photos, presentations, if applicable)

7.2.3 External Conferences and Events Template

The “External Conferences and Events Template” is an excel file (Annex 9), that partners may complete each time they identify an event (e.g. conference, workshop, seminar etc.) relevant to VIBES and in which VIBES partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Each partner should share this file with Q-PLAN, which will then be communicated to all project partners.

For each identified external conference or any other relevant event, each partner should indicate the following information:

- Event Name
- Thematic Focus
- Date and Location
- Registration Fees
- Specific requirements for participation
- Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)
- Link to event website
- Name of partner

8. Conclusions

This report provided the framework and guidelines for the successful implementation of communication, dissemination and training activities throughout the lifespan of the VIBES project and beyond. The report addressed what to communicate and disseminate, to whom, by what means and channels and when, as well as provided the monitoring framework that will be used for assessing the communication, dissemination and training activities, based on targeted KPIs.

By communicating and disseminating the project's tangible and intangible assets through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, VIBES will be able to not only go beyond its ambitious Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) but most importantly to lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes.

As the project evolves, the communication, dissemination and training plan will be updated and refined, providing a more detailed analysis of the communication, dissemination and training activities that will take place, in order to maximize the visibility and outreach of VIBES.

Annex 1. Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders

VIBES		Contact list of VIBES stakeholders									
Group list	Sub-group list	Group (please select from list on the left)	Sub-group (please select from list on the left)	Contact name	Gender (M/F)	Contact email	Organisation (if applicable)	Country	Nominated by VIBES consortium partner (name/organisation)	To be invited as Stakeholder Board member (yes/no/maybe)	Comments
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers										
	Composite recyclers										
	Other (please specify)										
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Aeronautical										
	Naval										
	Construction										
	Energy										
	Waste management										
	Logistics										
	Transport										
	Other (please specify)										
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Academics and/or Researchers										
	Technology and/or Innovation consultant										
	Other (please specify)										
Impact multipliers	Policy makers										
	Media/ journalists or bloggers										
	Other (please specify)										
Other (please specify)											

Annex 2. Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form

Declaration of Acceptance

(for individuals appointed as members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board in their individual capacity)

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the VIBES Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference.

I pledge that I will participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board in my individual capacity and as such I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium.

I certify that no conflict of interests exists that could be considered as prejudicial to my independence in acting as a member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the Stakeholders Board, unless the VIBES consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as member of the Stakeholders Board as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board may be used by the VIBES consortium for reporting purposes or to align the products and technologies offered by VIBES with the needs of final users to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are

We are contacting you in the framework of VIBES, a project funded by the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

VIBES aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

A detailed description of the project and description of how VIBES handles personal data is available through the project’s web site www.vibesproject.eu.

Project:

VIBES – Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology, based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials.

Project Coordinator:

Organisation name: FUNDACION AITIIP

Address: Polígono Industrial Empresarium, Calle Romero N°12, 50720 Zaragoza, Spain

Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager:

Organisation name: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Address: 11 El. Venizelou str, 55133 Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece.

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	Project Coordinator	Pere Castell	pere.castell@aitiip.com
2	Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager	Eirini Efthymiadou	info@vibesproject.eu ; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

What we need from you

We need you to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board with a view to participate in project activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and provide your views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

To effectively carry out the activities of the Stakeholders Board, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number).

- Some basic demographics (gender, nationality).
- Your professional information (organisation, job position, field of expertise).
- Your education information.
- Your opinions on the subject matter(s) of relevant events.

Why we need your data & what we will do with them

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out activities related to the Stakeholders Board and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of your participation in such activities. We also need to record your data to keep track of the implementation of the activities. The project’s deliverables that will be derived by activities in which you participate will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you.

We will share your data with other project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project’s evaluation.
- EU agencies and other authorities for project’s auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project activities and also to inform you about the project’s progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How you can withdraw your consent

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in the Stakeholders Board and its related activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, to provide my views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of VIBES.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding VIBES activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex 3. Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference

Introduction

You have been invited to take part in the **VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB)** because you were nominated by at least one of the VIBES consortium partners as a key stakeholder. The following Terms of Reference are aimed at helping you understand what this involves before you decide to participate. Please take the time to read this document carefully and ask for any clarifications you may require.

VIBES in a nutshell

VIBES is a 4-year Research and Innovation Action running from June 2021 to May 2025, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

The VIBES project aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative and cost-efficient **green technology solution** to resolve the **end-of-life issues of thermoset composites**, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. To reach its purpose, VIBES will initially focus on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised **100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)**. In addition, the project will design and develop biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to **place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market**. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/ cost ratio in 3 **high-demand industrial sectors**: aeronautical, construction and naval industries. Finally, a **greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology** to treat the smart VIBES composites will be developed and implemented at pilot level. As a result, the decomposed materials will be **recovered and valorised as new feedstocks** for the development of new products. The whole system will be defined, from the dismantling of the parts of the composite, to collecting and directing to the recycling plant, receiving, handling and sorting of the materials.

In this context, the Stakeholders Board (SB) of VIBES will consist of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings, who will be strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

The VIBES project brings together a consortium of **13 partners across 7 different EU member states**. You can find more information about VIBES and the consortium by visiting www.vibesproject.eu.

Role and benefits

Role

The SB is set up and operate to share its knowledge and expertise with the consortium of the project in key implementation stages. The role of the SB in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

- **Provide feedback and insights for the development process of VIBES innovations** such as the bio-based materials and the recycling technology, by participating in discussions and activities as prospective users of the developed materials and technology, to enhance their practical value and usability; as well as

- **Be actively involved in VIBES dissemination activities** to create a multiplier effect in spreading the word on the project's value propositions, knowledge and impact as well as facilitating the market uptake of the project's results.

To fulfil this role, it is foreseen that the SB, during the course of the project, will participate in VIBES demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and will interact on ad-hoc basis if necessary:

- **Demonstration workshop:** it is expected that the SB will help articulate and lead the organisation of at least one demonstration workshop, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept.
- **Roundtables:** it is expected that the SB will participate in at least two roundtables, to be organised at key turning points of the VIBES project, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation.
- **Technological breakfast:** it is expected that specific members of the SB will participate in at least one technological breakfast for industrial professionals, to be organised as part of the VIBES training programme, in order to share their views and experience in the fields addressed by the VIBES project.
- **Ad-hoc interactions:** if deemed necessary, the support of the SB (either in its entirety or of specific members based on their particular expertise) will be requested for ad hoc needs.

Benefits

The project provides **several benefits to its SB members**, such as:

- **Networking opportunities and visibility** as an expert stakeholder in a large multi-stakeholder community in the VIBES domain.
- **First access to meaningful insights, knowledge and results** generated exclusively within the context of the project and its activities.
- Unique opportunity to **align the VIBES bio-based materials and recycling technology with the needs of their stakeholders** to ensure that they make the most out of their value propositions.

Terms of membership and Management

Terms of membership

The SB shall be composed of eminent experts coming from diverse backgrounds to offer a blend of expertise that represents various groups of stakeholders from the VIBES whole value chain (such as industrial developers and users, academics and researchers, technology and innovation consultants, policy makers, media representatives etc.) and experts involved in projects and initiatives that are relevant to VIBES. These experts will provide VIBES with valuable feedback aimed at aligning the project's outcomes with the needs of users and stakeholders. Along these lines, at least 10 members of the Stakeholders Board (SB) will be initially selected with the possibility to further expand the SB in the future in order to draw from additional expertise and increase the outreach of VIBES. New members could be appointed to the SB when necessary and as the project evolves.

Although members of the SB may be selected because of their affiliations with key organisations, they serve on the SB in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities.

Members of the SB may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium. Members of the SB are appointed for the entire duration of the project (48 months, from 1 June 2021 to 31 May 2025). If due to job changes or attrition, an SB member loses links to important networks or constituencies, the consortium may decide to fill in this gap by appointing additional members.

The contribution of SB members is on a **pro bono basis**, apart from the cases in which physical travel is involved and a specific budget for their reimbursement is foreseen in the framework of the project. In such cases, the travel and accommodation expenses of SB members will be reimbursed by the project. Moreover, participation in the SB is **entirely voluntary**. There will be no adverse consequences if an SB member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, SB members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (see next section). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Management

The SB is managed by the **Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that facilitates the communications and interactions between the SB and the consortium, ensuring that SB members are not overloaded. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager will also ensure that for each task requiring input from the SB, the partners have beforehand prepared an action plan and all necessary briefings and material. Only then, will the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager introduce a partner who may directly communicate with the SB in order to achieve the expected goals at each time.

Contact point

Any enquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of your experience as a member of the Stakeholders Board (SB) can be addressed to the **VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that oversees the set up and manages the SB. The contact details of the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager are provided below:

VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Contact person: Eirini Efthymiadou

Phone: +30 2310 411 191

Email: info@vibesproject.eu; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

Project website: www.vibesproject.eu

Annex 4. Document and Presentation Templates

Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement 101023190

DX.Y “Title of Deliverable”
Work Package X
Responsible Partner: Name of Partner

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190.

 VIBES Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

www.vibesproject.eu

IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

Title
Location
Date

Name
Email
Organisation

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101023190.

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Chemistry
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IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

Title
Location
Date

Name
Email
Organisation

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101023190.

Annex 5. VIBES Presence on Social Media

VIBES Page on Twitter

←

VIBES Project 2021- 2025

7 Tweets

VIBES

www.vibesproject.eu

Edit profile

VIBES Project 2021- 2025
@VIBESU2

VIBES: an **#innovative** and **#cost-efficient** **#green** technology solution for **#thermoset** composites' end-of-life.
@BBI2020 @EU_H2020 funded project.

 Joined June 2021

19 Following **32** Followers

Tweets
Tweets & replies
Media
Likes

 Pinned Tweet

VIBES Project 2021- 2025 @VIBESU2 · Jun 18 ...

@BBI2020 @DrMNCollins New project starts, funded by BBI-JU under Horizon 2020: VIBES, a **#green** technology solution for **#thermoset** composites' end-of-life: bit.ly/3gzA110

#bioeconomy #circulareconomy #thermosetcomposites #greentechnology

VIBES Page on LinkedIn

VIBES Project 2021-2025
 A green technology solution for thermoset composites' end-of-life.
 Biotechnology · 42 followers

✓ Following More

Home About Posts Jobs People Videos

About

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. The project will develop a recycling solution that combines materials science...
 see more

See all details

Page posts

VIBES Project 2021-2025
 42 followers
 2mo · Edited · 🌐

VIBES: a green technology solution for thermoset composites' end-of-life. ...see more

VIBES Project 2021-2025
 42 followers
 4d · 🌐

A very interesting article, interviewing Dr Erik Frank of [German Institutes of Textile and Fiber Re](#): ...see more

VIBES Page on Facebook

VIBES Project 2021 - 2025
@VIBESProject2021 · Biotechnology company

Home · Reviews · Photos · Videos · **More**

33 total likes
39 total follows

Public posts at VIBES Project 2021 - 2025

VIBES Project 2021 - 2025 added a new photo to the album **VIBES Project**.
Published by Irini Efthimiadou · 27 August at 11:15 · 🌐

VIBES Project: explaining WHY, HOW and WHAT

- Decrease the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.
- Developing and demonstrating an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling solution.
- Design and development of bio-based materials.
- Validation in 3 high-demand industrial sectors.
- Scaling up optimized green recycling technology.
- Returning products obtained from recycling process to the market.

11 People reached · 0 Engagements · - Distribution score

Like · Comment · Share

VIBES Page on YouTube

VIBES Project

SUBSCRIBE

HOME

VIDEOS

PLAYLISTS

CHANNELS

DISCUSSION

ABOUT

Description

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. The project will develop a recycling solution that combines materials science developments and a green chemistry recycling technology.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union's Horizon2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101023190.

Stats

Joined Jul 26, 2021

VIBES Project

SUBSCRIBE

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ABOUT

Subscriptions

EuPC Association

78 subscribers

SUBSCRIBE

Recysite Project

165 subscribers

SUBSCRIBE

Annex 6. VIBES First Press Release

PRESS RELEASE

15/06/2021

New project starts, funded by BBI-JU under Horizon 2020: VIBES, a green technology solution for thermoset composites' end-of-life.

We are happy to announce the start of VIBES, a research & innovation project funded by Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI – JU) under the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon 2020, under Grant Agreement N° 101023190. With a duration of 48 months and a budget of almost 5.3 million Euros, the project held this week its kick-off meeting virtually.

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. The project will develop a recycling solution that combines materials science developments and a green chemistry recycling technology.

To reach its purpose, VIBES will initially focus on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised 100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM). In addition, the project will design and develop biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/cost ratio in 3 high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.

Finally, a greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology to treat the smart VIBES composites will be developed and implemented at pilot level. As a result, the decomposed materials will be recovered and valorised as new feedstocks for the development of new products. The whole system will be defined, from the dismantling of the parts of the composite, to collecting and directing to the recycling plant, receiving, handling and sorting of the materials.

The VIBES consortium, led by AITIIP (Spain), is comprised of 13 partners across 7 EU member states (Spain, France, Ireland, Germany, Belgium, Italy, Greece): 3 Research & Technology Organisations and 1 University (AITIIP, LEITAT, DITF, University of Limerick), 7 Small and Medium Enterprises (Specific Polymers, BCIRCULAR, FLIPS & DOBBELS, IDEC, Juno Composites, ARCHA, Q-PLAN International), 1 Large Company (ACCIONA Construcción), and 1 Public Body (Teruel International Airport PLATA).

Project Details

Grant Agreement No: 101023190

Start Date: 01/06/2021

Project Duration: 48 months

For additional information please contact:

- **Pere Castell** (VIBES Coordinator, AITIIP), e-mail: pere.castell@aitiip.com, phone: +34 976 464 544
- **Eirini Efthymiadou** (VIBES Communication and Stakeholders Manager, Q-PLAN International), e-mail: efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr, phone: +30 2310 411 191

Annex 7. Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

The form below has been designed to help keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activities of the project. As a reminder, communication and dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, conferences, fairs, forums, workshops, roundtables, press releases, newsletters, publications, presentations etc. Please, complete ANY RELEVANT PARTS of the form below each time you perform a communication or dissemination activity, either small or large.														
No.	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity	Title of conference, workshop, publication, article, etc.	Type of audience	Size of audience (no. of persons per stakeholders group if possible)	Countries addressed	Role and description of partner organisation's involvement (e.g. facilitator, speaker, author, participant, etc.)	Type of project promotional material used (e.g. leaflets, infographic poster or roll-out, project presentation, etc.)	Quantity of project promotional material used (no. of copies distributed per type of material)	Other VIBES partners or external organisations responsible / involved	Short description of the activity	Other comments	Significant contacts made (name, position, organisation; <u>if consent to store and share data was given</u> , add also address, tel, fax, e-mail)
1														
2														
3														

Annex 8. Event Reporting Form

Event's Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type, including % of female attendees)	
Duration	

Event's goals, objectives and relevance to VIBES

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). Was the event relevant to VIBES? To what extent?

Organisation of the event

This section is completed only in case of organising a project event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organised?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Promotional activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the VIBES project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observation that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

Annexes: Attachments

If applicable, the following Annexes should be attached:

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if applicable)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g. leaflets, infographic, newsletters etc.)

Annex 9. External Conferences and Events Template

		Identified External Conferences and Events							
No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Date	Location	Registration fees	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission etc)	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Added by (Partner)
1									
2									
3									